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SECURITY THREATS ON CLOUD COMPUTING VULNERABILITIES

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ABSTRACT

Clouds provide a powerful computing platform that enables individuals and organizations to perform variety levels of tasks such as: use of online storage space, adoption of business applications, development of customized computer software, and creation of a “realistic” network environment. In previous years, the number of people using cloud services has dramatically increased and lots of data has been stored in cloud computing environments. In the meantime, data breaches to cloud services are also increasing every year due to hackers who are always trying to exploit the security vulnerabilities of the architecture of cloud. In this paper, three cloud service models were compared; cloud security risks and threats were investigated based on the nature of the cloud service models. Real world cloud attacks were included to demonstrate the techniques that hackers used against cloud computing systems. In addition, countermeasures to cloud security breaches are presented.

KEYWORDS

Cloud computing, cloud security threats and countermeasures, cloud service models

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DATA WAREHOUSE AND BIG DATA INTEGRATION

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ABSTRACT

Big Data triggered furthered an influx of research and prospective on concepts and processes pertaining previously to the Data Warehouse field. Some conclude that Data Warehouse as such will disappear; others present Big Data as the natural Data Warehouse evolution (perhaps without identifying a clear division between the two); and finally, some others pose a future of convergence, partially exploring the possible integration of both. In this paper, we revise the underlying technological features of Big Data and Data Warehouse, highlighting their differences and areas of convergence. Even when some differences exist, both technologies could (and should) be integrated because they both aim at the same purpose: data exploration and decision making support. We explore some convergence strategies, based on the common elements in both technologies. We present a revision of the state-of-the-art in integration proposals from the point of view of the purpose, methodology, architecture and underlying technology, highlighting the common elements that support both technologies that may serve as a starting point for full integration and we propose a proposal of integration between the two technologies.

KEYWORDS

Big Data, Data Warehouse, Integration, Hadoop, NoSql, MapReduce, 7V's, 3C's, M&G

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CLUSTERING ALGORITHM FOR A HEALTHCARE DATASET USING SILHOUETTE SCORE VALUE

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ABSTRACT

The huge amount of healthcare data, coupled with the need for data analysis tools has made data mining interesting research areas. Data mining tools and techniques help to discover and understand hidden patterns in a dataset which may not be possible by mainly visualization of the data. Selecting appropriate clustering method and optimal number of clusters in healthcare data can be confusing and difficult most times. Presently, a large number of clustering algorithms are available for clustering healthcare data, but it is very difficult for people with little knowledge of data mining to choose suitable clustering algorithms. This paper aims to analyze clustering techniques using healthcare dataset, in order to determine suitable algorithms which can bring the optimized group clusters. Performances of two clustering algorithms (Kmeans and DBSCAN) were compared using Silhouette score values. Firstly, we analyzed K-means algorithm using different number of clusters (K) and different distance metrics. Secondly, we analyzed DBSCAN algorithm using different minimum number of points required to form a cluster (minPts) and different distance metrics. The experimental result indicates that both K-means and DBSCAN algorithms have strong intra-cluster cohesion and inter-cluster separation. Based on the analysis, K-means algorithm performed better compare to DBSCAN algorithm in terms of clustering accuracy and execution time.

KEYWORDS

Dataset, Clustering, Healthcare data, Silhouette score value, K-means, DBSCAN

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ONLINE LEARNING DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC, AND POSSIBILITY OF ADOPTING COMPUTER-BASED TEST

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ABSTRACT

Clouds provide a powerful computing platform that enables individuals and organizations to perform variety levels of tasks such as: use of online storage space, adoption of business applications, development of customized computer software, and creation of a “realistic” network environment. In previous years, the number of people using cloud services has dramatically increased and lots of data has been stored in cloud computing environments. In the meantime, data breaches to cloud services are also increasing every year due to hackers who are always trying to exploit the security vulnerabilities of the architecture of cloud. In this paper, three cloud service models were compared; cloud security risks and threats were investigated based on the nature of the cloud service models. Real world cloud attacks were included to demonstrate the techniques that hackers used against cloud computing systems. In addition, countermeasures to cloud security breaches are presented.

KEYWORDS

E-learning, COVID-19, online education, Computer-Based Exams, Computer test.

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DATA MINING MODEL PERFORMANCE OF SALES PREDICTIVE ALGORITHMS BASED ON RAPIDMINER WORKFLOWS

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ABSTRACT

By applying RapidMiner workflows has been processed a dataset originated from different data files, and containing information about the sales over three years of a large chain of retail stores. Subsequently, has been constructed a Deep Learning model performing a predictive algorithm suitable for sales forecasting. This model is based on artificial neural network –ANN- algorithm able to learn the model starting from sales historical data and by pre-processing the data. The best built model uses a multilayer neural network together with an “optimized operator” able to find automatically the best parameter setting of the implemented algorithm. In order to prove the best performing predictive model, other machine learning algorithms have been tested. The performance comparison has been performed between Support Vector Machine –SVM-, k-Nearest Neighbor k-NN-, Gradient Boosted Trees, Decision Trees, and Deep Learning algorithms. The comparison of the degree of correlation between real and predicted values, the average absolute error and the relative average error proved that ANN exhibited the best performance. The Gradient Boosted Trees approach represents an alternative approach having the second best performance. The case of study has been developed within the framework of an industry project oriented on the integration of high performance data mining models able to predict sales using –ERP- and customer relationship management –CRM- tools.

KEYWORDS

RapidMiner, Neural Network, Deep Learning, Gradient Boosted Trees, Data Mining Performance, Sales Prediction.

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AN EXPLORATION OF THE FACTORS AFFECTING USERS' SATISFACTION WITH MOBILE PAYMENTS

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ABSTRACT

Mobile payment allows consumers to make more flexible payments through convenient mobile devices. While mobile payment is easy and time save, the operation and security of mobile payment must ensure that the payment is fast, convenient, reliable and safety in order to increase the users' satisfaction. Therefore, this study based on technology acceptance model to explore the impact of external variables through perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use on users' satisfaction. The data analysis methods used in this study are descriptive statistical analysis, reliability and validity analysis, Pearson correlation analysis and regression analysis to verify the hypotheses. The results show that all hypotheses are supported. However, mobile payment is still subject to many restrictions on development and there are limited related researches. The results of this study provided insight into the factors that affect the users' satisfaction for mobile payment. Related services development of mobile payment and future research suggestions are also offered.

KEYWORDS

Mobile Payment, Technology Acceptance Model, Users' satisfaction

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RISK MANAGEMENT FRAMEWORKS FOR CLOUD COMPUTING: A CRITICAL REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Cloud computing technology has experienced exponential growth over the past few years. It provides many advantages for both individuals and organizations. However, at the same time, many issues have arisen due to the vast growth of cloud computing. Organizations often have concerns about the migration and utilization of cloud computing due to the loss of control over their outsourced resources and cloud computing is vulnerable to risks. Thus, a cloud provider needs to manage the cloud computing environment risks in order to identify, assess, and prioritize the risks in order to decrease those risks, improve security, increase confidence in cloud services, and relieve organizations' concerns on the issue of using a cloud environment. Considering that a conventional risk management framework does not fit well with cloud computing due to the complexity of its environment, research in this area has become widespread. The aim of this paper is to review the previously proposed risk management frameworks for cloud computing and to make a comparison between them in order to determine the strengths and weaknesses of each of them. The review will consider the extent of the involvement and participation of consumers in cloud computing and other issues.

KEYWORDS

Cloud Computing; Risk Management & Information Security

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A SYSTEMATIC MAPPING STUDY ON CURRENT RESEARCH TOPICS IN SMART CONTRACTS

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ABSTRACT

An appealing feature of blockchain technology is smart contracts. A smart contract is executable code that runs on top of the blockchain to facilitate, execute and enforce an agreement between untrusted parties without the involvement of a trusted third party. In this paper, we conduct a systematic mapping study to collect all research that is relevant to smart contracts from a technical perspective. The aim of doing so is to identify current research topics and open challenges for future studies in smart contract research. We extract 24 papers from different scientific databases. The results show that about two thirds of the papers focus on identifying and tackling smart contract issues. Four key issues are identified, namely, codifying, security, privacy and performance issues. The rest of the papers focuses on smart contract applications or other smart contract related topics. Research gaps that need to be addressed in future studies are provided.

KEYWORDS

Blockchain, Smart contracts, Systematic mapping study, Survey

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ENVIRONMENTAL MONITORING AND CONTROLLING SYSTEM FOR MUSHROOM FARM WITH ONLINE INTERFACE

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ABSTRACT

Agriculture sensors play an important role in modern agriculture. The use of sensors in various agriculture sectors minimizes the environmental impact on crops, helps in increasing yield and saving cost of operation. Among all agriculture industries in Malaysia, the mushroom industry is a comparatively new and small. As most of the mushroom farms in Malaysia are small-scaled, their production capability is limited by inadequate environmental control system and the lack of financial resources to upgrade the systems. This paper presents an environmental monitoring and controlling system to monitor and control the environmental conditions in a mushroom farm. It enables user to monitor temperature, humidity, carbon dioxide concentration and light intensity in a mushroom farm on an android device by using ThingSpeak online platform. The control algorithm is able to control devices in a mushroom farm automatically based on feedback from the sensors to maintain the environment in an optimum condition for mushroom growth. The measured percentage error of temperature, humidity, carbon dioxide and the light using the developed system was as low as 0.4%, 1.5%, 2.2% and 1.34% respectively

KEYWORDS

Agriculture, Interface Circuit, Internet of Things, Monitoring and Control, Sensor, Wireless.

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DETECTION OF MALARIA PARASITE IN GIEMSA BLOOD SAMPLE USING IMAGE PROCESSING

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ABSTRACT

Malaria is one of the deadliest diseases ever exists in this planet. Automated evaluation process can notably decrease the time needed for diagnosis of the disease. This will result in early onset of treatment saving many lives. As it poses a serious global health problem, we approached to develop a model to detect malaria parasite accurately from giemsa blood sample with the hope of reducing death rate because of malaria. In this work, we developed a model by using color based pixel discrimination technique and Segmentation operation to identify malaria parasites from thin smear blood images. Various segmentation techniques like watershed segmentation, HSV segmentation have been used in this method to decrease the false result in the area of malaria detection. We believe that, our malaria parasite detection method will be helpful wherever it is difficult to find the expert in microscopic analysis of blood report and also limits the human error while detecting the presence of parasites in the blood sample.

KEYWORDS

Malaria, HSV segmentation, Watershed segmentation, Giemsa blood sample, RBC.

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